

Company Innovative Leadership Model

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Introduction

What is leadership? This question has been the object of investigation for social researchers for much of that 20th century and still there is no universally agreed-upon.

Definition of leadership

A large number of definitions have been advanced by spoolers. The care concept of almost all created and developed definitions involves the notion of influence. Leader influence other to pool effect to work towards achieving a particular aim the difficulty to provide a single definition of leadership comes to from the too broad scope of the term the effects and includes a big number of qualities, competences, skills, approaches, reaction and situations. Yet there is a definition which the globe (House et al.,2004) agreed upon and it real states that the leadership is the ability of an individual to influence, motivate and enable other to contribute toward the effectiveness and success of the organizations of which they are member (House et al.,2004, p.15).

Leadership of a company

What is the company’s leadership – why is it different from the personal leadership and what does it exactly mean?

Company leadership is not the same as personal leadership. In the company’s meaning, leadership is not related to personal and competences. Is the assumption true that a company is a leader due to its leaders? It might be true but there are a lot of examples that prove the contrary. They are companies that are able to build leaders on their own or to run the business irrespective of person at the helm of the company or at least not due to leader’s quantities and actions. Usually these companies have a long history, a large board of directors a wide product range, loyal customers, brands that have become house hold names for the market segment.A leader is someone who leads or commands a group or an organization. The meaning of leader could equal with a manager.

Leadership honor is the ability to make people important some idea or work towards goal. In the sense of company leadership suggests a company’s ability and desire to be in the first positions by different criteria and accordingly be recognized as a leading company. In other words the company’s leading position in a sector is a consequence of its leadership ability. Some other perspectives reveal company leadership as the ability to set the direction of development in the sector of rearrange market shares with in the sector or launch new trends in the sector. In this study all theories are generalized and company leadership is assumed to be the company ability to be a leader in the respective business sector. Some of the most valuable indices are; Dow Jones indices, Forbes, NASDAQ, S&P 500 index among other indices. The indicators that reincorporated in indices net and operating profit, investment, return, market share, product diversity, growth quality, social environment, social incentives employment engagement ect. The evaluation could be performed annually, quarterly, or could be based on periodical data or cover a long period of time.

Indicators	Details
Market share (%)	As a percentage in the sector
Size of assets (M)	According to balance sheet
Volume of investments (in 3y)	Volume of investments in last 3year according to profit and loss account
Number of employs	How many employs work in the organization
Sales revenue (M)	According to turnover report
EBITDA (M)	Earnings before interest, tax, depreciation and amortization
Net profit (M)	The difference between operational (EBITDA) and net profit is the sum of interest, tax, depreciation and amortization, which a part of the leadership management and their management should be taken into consideration
Profit before tax (EBT) (M)	In decides financial management of a company for all financial services interactions and practices
EBITDA margin	EBITDA/sales revenue
EBITDA change (%)	Change in EBITDA(%) form previous year
Equity (M)	According to balance sheet
Debt ratio (leverage)	Ratio of liabilities to equity
ROE (return if equity)	Net profit/equity

Company innovative leadership model

An innovative company is not some kind of specific company, innovative in stricture or with organization representation; it generates innovation thought innovative ways. A company innovative is an integral part of its characteristics, competences and mostly The Company innovative leadership model aims at evaluating the companies’ innovative capability and performance. It contains 12 criteria the innovation in indicators falls into three main groups; indicators measuring the company innovation activity, indicator measuring the company innovations potential and indicators measuring the company innovation competencies.

Innovation Competences

- Competency is a persistent pattern of behavior resulting from a cluster of knowledge, skill, abilities, and motivations (Boyd et al., 2011). Prahalad and heal (prahalad and homely,

2006, pp.79-91) define it as “harmonized combination of multiple resources and skill that distinguish a firm in the market place” in their research both scholars arrive at the conclusion that ambition and desire for building competences is what characterizes global winners. The concept of competences was developed by McClelland (McClelland, 1973, pp-1-24) first in 1973 and later on was clarified by Boyatzis (1982) in 1982.

- The latter can be revealed only by set of creative such as skills, knowledge, abilities and motivations some of innovate competences a: creativity (generating ideas, critical thinking, and creative problem solving), managing change (sensitivity to situations, challenging the status quo, intelligent risk-taking, reinforcing change), integrating perspectives (openness to ideas, resource orientations, collaborating), enterprising (identifying problem seeking improvement, gathering information independent thinking, technologic savvy, result orientation), etc. (Boyd, 2011).

Innovation Potential and Capabilities

In these sections matrices are organized in five subgroups for indicator. The section aims at measuring the company innovative potential as well as thru company current innovation related performance. The categories among which the different criteria are allocated are. Flexibility, social skills and commences Platform and date leadership, strategy business process.

Layout

- Trend raising
- social
- Platform and data
- Leadership
- Strategy, planning and policies
- Resource and development cost and investment
- Employees in R&B
- Number of introduced product/process/ marketing organizational
- Ratio between the number of innovation
- R&D expenditure as a share of total revenue
- Registered, trademarks, patents, new designing
- training and educational improvement

(1) Trending rising

If the trend is rising, then the company reaction to the markets and its innovative capabilities are good enough.

(2) Social

- Social capabilities, communication and marketing and skills and associate data with these activities, complaints to build more powerful relationship with customer. the measured criterion that exposes a company innovate capabilities is how much have a company benefits from using main social interaction channels with potential customers to predict and forecast trends.
- The main channels faces book from office /shops, questions to customers faces book, tweeter, LinkedIn social net works, own company website, user drive innovation, test customers groups in Per-sales stages CRM, direct marketing, etc.
- If it uses 1 or 2 of the channels – then the company revs points from 10 the most innovative companies this criterion are expected to use or possible
- channels for interaction with customers

(3) Platform and data

- Platform and data combine software, hard work, data analytics that allow companies to developed and manage at eco system of customers, partners or developers and to manage by optimum way the interactions between all dependencies which can possibly stem from those main factors.
- This criterion is measured by counting how many of the following platforms and data bases the company use: customers data bases, product database /catalog, process system, online trade channel, automatic and smart process CRM, time process measurement software, ect.

(4) Leadership

Leadership might be a significant factor that allows companies to make dramatic moves onto new markets and innovations. This indicators is measured by evaluating the companies leadership practical's if the there are policies for development leaders, coaching and mentoring programs then the company should be awarded the full point by this criterion the is measured by dichotomous base depend on exiting and such kind of leadership practices or the lack when a comparison among several companies is made, them more complicated scale should be applied by comparing the number of used procedures and the result they bring.

(5) Strategy, planning and policies

- Refers to the collection of innovation methods and reveal companies as pioneers.
- Innovations development policy, R&D departments, decision making on innovation product and processes, innovation processes developments each policy bring one point.
- The scale consists of 10 points in basic measurement and might be extended when a comparison between several companies is realized.

Innovation activity

The third group of criteria is the well-known innovation metrics that uses some specific practices in companies. Such metrics are used in the innovation scoreboard and other innovation measurement indices.

(6) Research and development costs and investment

Research and development costs and investment are any expenses associated with the research and development of a company goods or services R&D expenses are a type of operating expenses and are incurred in the process of finding and creating new products or services.

(7) Employees in R&D

Departments or terms employees with innovation ideas from last 12 month – how many employees devoted to innovation activities.

(8) Number of introduction

The criterion directly reveals the company innovative activity ably some one compurgation with innovation product on could be accomplished or with innovated project still under construction.

(9) Ratio between the number of innovation made in-house and the number of innovation made innovation collaboration

With some third parties academic institutes, universities, innovated companies, consultants, customers, open innovation user-driven innovation, public sector, ect.

(10) R &D expenditure as a share of total revenue

- This metric, also called Red / scale ratio is useful to compare the effectiveness and efficiency of R&D expenditure between companies in the same industry.
- In the meaning of the company's innovative leadership model, the criterion measures not effectiveness only but also innovation effects.

(11) Registered tread marks, patents, new designs

- That criterion provides information about legal and registration procedures that a company has taken during the last year about its innovation
- The result shows how the company ensures protection of its innovation and its activities as performed

(12) Training and educational improvements

- (Degrees, diplomas) of the employees (number of activities/ number of employees) -innovative companies rely on its team innovativeness and that is why the company should train and improve the skills, knowledge and competencies of the employees.
- The criterion shows the type and number of training program and educational improvements employees attend.
- The criterion is organized as an index order to eliminate any size or industry- related dependency.
- The methodology for measuring leading innovative companies ensures well- balanced results. The reason why this approach has been chosen is that a lot of company's running its business in particular economic fields tend to apply one tool more than the other. These companies cannot pursue a stable long – term innovative policy and ensure sustainable performance.

How does the company innovative leadership model differ from the other ones and what value does it bring to companies

- They are a lot of indices aimed at indexing and evaluating the innovativeness no one of them emphasizes on the leading position of innovative company or innovation leadership.
- Most of them just distinguish innovative and ordinary organizations by some criteria. Actually the commonly employed innovativeness, but the innovativeness of a sector or even of a country. That is why for a company it is difficult to analyze what effects should be made in order to achieve innovativeness.
- These are what the leading innovative company modal guarantees if encompass 12 factor that expose the company innovative performance, capabilities and competencies and allow for making some competence, whether between two or more companies between the company and its sector, amongst sectors, ect. This comparison is made possible by the commonly used indices to measure innovation leadership.
- The innovation union score board measure three main types of indicators and eight innovation dimensions, capturing in total 25 different indicators.
- It aims at measuring macro level innovation performance. As a result, the innovation union score board use on over view of the innovation activities and effects of EU member countries. They are clustered in four categories: innovation leaders, innovation followers, moderate innovator, and modest innovator, where exactly has been placed Bulgaria.

Leading innovative company's profit

A company might pleased at the top according this model if it flow as and uses those principals in its innovation activities, polices and performance

1. It should be flexible to the market, customer technical and environment circumstances. This flexibility should be visible in the sales revenue growth each year.
2. Social capabilities and communication with all other innovator in the business are essential. The strong and well controlled relations build long- lasting and stable business environment in an otherwise unstable business world. Company should use all possible integration channels with internal and external environment to collect feedback, to communicate effectively.
3. As gentle rule the data hidden the most impartment information in itself. It just must be grinded, structured, analyzed and used. Now days there is a long number of soft doing that a high performed company by the leading innovative muddle uses at minimum those method for summarizing and applying the valve of the information: customer data base product database/catalog, process system, online tread channel, automatic and smart process, CRM, time process measurement software, ect.
4. Leadership is one of the strongest and useful tools for boosting a company to an innovation. The leadership itself is a capability of gaining followers. That is why the personal or companies leadership is often used for the purpose of increasing the innovativeness with in an organizations.

Website

1. <http://www.oecdpublising.org>